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EDUCATING A NEW GENERATION OF INNOVATORS THROUGH AN INTERDISCIPLINARY DESIGN PROGRAM IN CHINA

A CASE STUDY ON THE INFORMATION ART AND DESIGN INTERDISCIPLINARY PROGRAM AT TSINGHUA UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

The thoughts and practices for educating the new generation of Chinese designers to meet sustained growth and inclusive development in China is the focus of this paper. Three institutes at Tsinghua University in China co-established the interdisciplinary master's program, Information Art and Design, in 2009. We created a new research framework for this program to identify the opportunities of social and business innovation, integrate the methodologies based on design thinking, and frame the multi-entrance educational model. The exploration, thoughts and lessons on team building, project management, knowledge construction and integrated innovation will hopefully be a good reference for building similar programs.

Keywords: Design education, interdisciplinary program, integrated innovation.

INTRODUCTION

Facing the increasingly complicated development of society, economy and technology, the crossover and integration of disciplines is becoming the new trend for the development of high-level education. In 2002, the Report Converging Technologies for Improving Human Performance, formulated jointly by the US National Science Foundation and the US Department of Commerce, holds the viewpoint that "The sciences have reached a watershed at which they must unify if they are to continue to advance rapidly."

These days, many famous universities, e.g., Massachusetts Institute of Technology and Harvard

University, have established interdisciplinary research centers. The training of interdisciplinary talents has become the standard mode for educational innovation. In 1998, the Departments of Fine Arts, Modern Culture, Social Engineering, Structural Engineering and Electronic & Information of Tsukuba University in Japan jointly created a special study program, "Modeling the Evaluation Structure of Kansei". With the support of interdisciplinary strength, the Program was housed in a separate building for joint research. Research teams were composed of staff from each interdisciplinary profession and integrated fine arts, Kansei engineering and cyber robot, building a unique interdisciplinary design and research field. Carnegie Mellon University in the US offers many interdisciplinary courses in its School of Design and has established different graduate programs that cross over schools and departments. For instance, Communication Planning and Information Design is a program offered with the collaboration of the Department of English, while Product Development is offered with the Mechanical Engineering Department and the Business School. Similarly, Tsukuba University develops interdisciplinary teaching and graduate training among multiple disciplines and supports joint interdisciplinary research. The design and innovation that emerge from many current significant projects indicate that interdisciplinary talents are more capable of integrating and innovating and that an interdisciplinary team is more useful in producing creative outcomes. For instance, many technology-oriented IT corporations, in the phases of product R&D, design and testing, have introduced

anthropologists and psychologists to assist in developing new tech products. Led by innovative thinking, culture and technology started a new integration. Such interdisciplinary cooperation makes each discipline a full participant and provides new products and services consumers' need.

In September 2009, the Academy of Arts & Design of Tsinghua University cooperated with the Department of Computer Science and the School of Journalism and Communication to start an Interdisciplinary Master Program in "Information Art and Design". The new program, based on the needs of industrial development of national cultural creation, educates new creative talents in art and design with an international vision in the fields of digital media, information and interaction design. By integrating literature and engineering, arts with technology, the program educates students with multi-disciplinary backgrounds with a focus on design, technology and media. See figure 1. It stresses the importance of design thinking, planning management and integrated innovation both in teaching and practice, in addition to collaborations with companies on project-driven courses.

Figure 1. Interdisciplinary program education system

As for the training of interdisciplinary graduates, the most important is to establish suitable development orientation, cultivation mode and teaching system, which define the goal and field of this program as well as to make it a sustainable, open and vigorous education system for high-level talents.

THE ORIENTATION OF THIS PROGRAM

Peter Drucker, a management guru, points out in his book *Managing in the Next Society* that in the past 40–50 years, economy was the driving force; but in the coming 20-30 years, social issues will become the leading force. A researcher of social innovation in the UK, Geoff Mulgan who was director of the Policy Department of the Prime Minister's Office, points out in his book that the most significant innovation in the future will not come from information science or the insurance sector, but the social sector.

Chinese society is unprecedented in its diversity today. A large proportion of low-incomers and few nouveaux riches with powerful strength, as well as the growing middle bourgeoisie which is less in numbers, are experiencing double changes in terms of culture and economy. Chinese society is developing from a centralized society to a more open society. Local socialized media also plays an important role, e.g., many government agencies, famous people, experts and managers in all fields have their IDs in Microblog. New and old concepts from eastern and western cultures fight fiercely in the virtual world. Meanwhile, society and culture of China begin to emerge into the world gradually. These changes have brought about new challenges for our design research and practice.

Interdisciplinary projects of information art and design place importance on interaction design, service design and social innovation, based on digital media and network technology. The projects highlight the integration of design & information science with humanity and social sciences in terms of theory and methodology, as well as the influence of design innovation to society and industry.

Social innovation is the major driver for social change and development in each country under globalization. The program focuses on interaction design and service design, based on social media and social integration. Recent research projects include one for Nokia "Happy Life", which was designed for the low-incomers, with applications including farm assistance on mobile phones to help farmers connect with citizens for direct sales of agricultural products. Project "Luck gravida" focuses on a special group of people, pregnant women, and helps them better manage their own fertility files and establish connection with hospitals. We also have, together

with Motorola China, undertaken a study on the development trends of Chinese social networking and discussed how to design the application of mobile social media in the context of Chinese society and culture. The information architecture courses, which we cooperated with New York Parsons for Design on, examined Urban Media as the subject, extending the vision to urban size, dividing it into traffic facilities, energy, safety and environmental protection etc. and exploring new changes in urban life possibly brought about by information interaction and service design.

In the courses of project practice, we divided the design process into several stages, define opportunities, understand, conceptualize, and implementation. It shows that design's goal is not only to create a product, but also provide an integrated and innovative solution. In the teaching and training, it is most important to discover new chances to be able to execute the innovation by using all available skills. However, solving the issue of design convergence needs not only adherence to the literal definition of design and consideration of local culture, but also cross-border design thinking and integrated methodology.

METHOD OF CROSS-BORDER DESIGN THINKING

The problems we face, in the new century, are getting more complex, ill-defined, ambiguous and associated with strong moral, political and professional issues, i.e., wicked problem. Design innovation tends to use a new logic, which is to develop deduction and reasoning into exploration. In the process of constant exploration, develop an understanding of objects and then finally form the most proper solutions. In current interdisciplinary innovation, "Design Thinking" has become the common methodology of team working. It changes not only product development, services process, but also conceptual strategy.

In 2008, Tim Brown, the CEO of the US design consultant IDEO, published *Design Thinking* in the Harvard Business Review, regarding design thinking as a tool for the solution to commercial, social and cultural innovation. Tim Brown holds the view that design thinking can be described as a method which uses designers' perception and methods to meet people's needs through series techniques of

exploration, ideation and implementation. Design thinking also transfers the outcomes into consumers' value and market chances through feasible business strategy.

In some comprehensive universities in the world, the interdisciplinary master's programs of integrating design, technology and business are standing out. These programs educate graduates by introducing the concept of design thinking, which helps designer and manager deal with complicated challenges. Currently, there are not only design education tests undergoing in design colleges, but also examples of increasing design innovation training in MBA programs in business schools. For instance, the D-School at Stanford University integrates experts from anthropology, business and technology and builds teams that engage in interdisciplinary research of design innovation by cultural cooperation and integrating different scientific viewpoints.

INTEGRATED PLATFORM

The innovation needed in transforming commerce, society, and culture will surely lead to the innovation of education for graduates. In an interdisciplinary environment, cultivating students' innovative capability is key for the development of research universities. "Interdisciplinary Supervisor group" or "interdisciplinary innovation platform" will become key factors for education and design research for graduates.

The interdisciplinary courses of "information art and design" for graduates include fundamental courses, studio, seminar and a certain number of selective courses. In the practical courses, professors and students discuss design together and seek innovative solutions jointly in the process of research. This sets up several subjects (interaction art/design, social innovation, digital entertainment design) in the practical courses. Graduates are tutored to complete the subjects in the form of an Supervisor group. Project subjects are determined through a discussion among the Supervisor group. Subjects should be interdisciplinary, can make use of the theories and methods of each discipline comprehensively and be completed jointly by interdisciplinary student teams. Seminars are supplementary courses, which support academic inquiry. Replacing lectures by reading, discussion and conversation, encourages students to

form their own design methodology and philosophy through the group interaction in class. The elective courses of each discipline can meet the needs of individual education and more extensive knowledge of the graduates.

Interdisciplinary supervisor group should proactively build up common area among multiple disciplines, and then work together to provide every course with practical subject perspectives and knowledge fields based on this common area. So these courses will achieve more than a typical single course. Hence, in the Program, Supervisors' collaboration and joint research are very important. The basis for collaboration among Supervisors is the Interdisciplinary project. This Program adopts the pattern of joint Supervisors who are thesis Supervisor and project/course Supervisor. The selection of Supervisor is according to the graduation degree. There is only project/course Supervisor in the first term, determined by the courses. In the second term, graduates begin to discuss their own direction and select thesis Supervisors and project Supervisors. Project practice, graduation thesis and design research are directed by joint Supervisor groups. A thesis Supervisor is responsible for the final degree; a project Supervisor is responsible for joint instruction and completing the interdisciplinary design project.

The other highlight of interdisciplinary training is that graduates can study and research in teams. Team members can achieve an interdisciplinary system by crossing over traditional boundaries; can express their opinions, discuss concepts, and self-assess freely. Everyone on the team will not only add to their professional knowledge, but also learn and grow constantly. Students from different backgrounds support and learn from each other in the team and become more secure in the practice of design. Moreover, in the process of the project, they are able to understand a complicated project as a whole, and master the ability of coordinating various sources and managing design/innovation progress. At present, the Program has accepted around 30 students in two years with majors in art/design, journalism, literature, computer science, automation and electronic engineering. The students are recommended mainly from the Tsinghua University. Some are from entry exams to make the students

diversified. In future years, they will follow the model of “multi-entries, one platform (educational process) and multi-exits (graduation degrees)”. See Figure 2.

Figure 2. Model for Interdisciplinary Graduate education

One of the features of the Program is multiple graduation degree. Differing from most other interdisciplinary master programs of design in the world, the Program provides three departments/disciplines to graduate from. This allows the graduates to select on their own department/discipline, to make use of the advantages of different disciplines, and strengthen the training for individualism. The advantage is that this relates closely to actual industry employment. When students graduate, they can introduce design thinking into the industries like media and computer. For example, three design background graduates chose computer science as their graduation discipline, they needed to finish the courses and practices of computer science in the second year. When design background students change their major and transfer to computer science discipline, they will be trained to obtain the capabilities of computing thinking and learn to develop and manage products based on the logical and quantitative techniques. The other feature of the Program is that it is project driven. Graduate teams must complete the design project, which is visualized and exhibited, emphasizing the connection to a product and service application, and providing a realization of social and industrial innovation.

CASE STUDY

"Project Practice", a series of courses, was established to meet the comprehensive and innovative needs of student teams. Three separate project-driven courses are involved in this series, which focus on design methodology learning, practical application, and integrated innovation. In the course Project 1, we arrange the students participate in the research project with Motorola on mobile SNS and design project with Nokia on service design for the low-income people in China. In Project 2, the information structure methods are introduced for an *Urban Media* system design. In Project 3, there are teams working on the intelligent Cubes product development, information visualization based on data mining, show clear characteristics of interdisciplinary innovation. Two design cases from course Project 3 will be explained below.

CASE A: INTELLIGENT CUBES

This group of graduates comes from Media Art and Electrical Engineering background. They initially conceived a lot of ideas, but not enough to satisfy themselves. A week later, they suddenly got inspired when playing with a rubber eraser. They decided to make the intelligent robots, which can jump and communicate with each other.

This typical inspirational thinking that is a kind of "thinking in the moment", students need the hard study, long-term practice and continuous accumulating experience to reach this status.

At the beginning of the project, the student with the media art background, paid more attention to the meaning and the novelty of the idea, while the student with the engineering background devoted his attention to the function and physical structure. Through communicating and negotiating in team, they reached a consensus on the concept and developed the basic functional requirements of the product. Next, they had to deal with the technology. At this stage, the media art student continuously put forward new ideas, but the technology student controlled the process of implementation. Finally, they developed several prototypes. Each one has emoticons and jumping functions. See Figure 3. They will continue adding more social functions to this product. As a result, the Cubes with more social

network functions will be presented at the first Beijing international design triennial this October.

Figure 3. Case A: Intelligent cubes

The achievement of this project helps the team understand their potentials. During the development process, I facilitate the students to think about more opportunities. Just like one student said, "I feel that innovation is an ongoing thing. In fact, innovation is just like an iceberg. The main part is far below the surface, not to be seen on the water. People usually think that part of the exposed surface of the water is innovation, but ignoring the more important things underwater. There was a significant difference between creativity and innovation. Creativity means make things from nothing. Innovation, however, is the extension or implementation based on the old one."

Through the investigation and tracking of the whole design process, we found that in a team, effective communication comes from the respect of each other's backgrounds, learning from each other, and mutually sharing the benefits. Student always have lots of ideas, but one good will be enough. In an interdisciplinary project, technology may help an artist's ideas come true, but may give more challenges to the technology background student. In a team project with different background students participating, the discussions and ideas may offer challenges and restrictions. This will increase difficult demands for the technology student. For example, designing a circuit board with a limited size or form to meet the aesthetic requirements of the artist will be difficult. But these new difficulties really give students the opportunity to enhance their professional knowledge and experience.

CASE B: INFORMATION VISUALIZATION

This project was part of a data-mining project of the computer science department. The basic data processing of the *RenRen.com* website (the biggest social network website in China) was finished before our graduates join this project. The interdisciplinary team includes the technology and visual communication background students, they are asked to analyze the data and offer new ideas on data visualization.

Differing greatly from interactive products with concrete shapes and explicit contexts, the visualization project didn't have a reference and imaginative prototype. Students didn't have experience with and even the suitable language to describe the possible deliverable of this project. The biggest challenges were how to imagine the final results, how to begin the discussion inside the interdisciplinary team and how to build a basic prototype based on their common understanding. At the very beginning, students only had a blurred description and perception of the final goal. They began to envision the value and function through analyzing and comparing the related SNS information graph. Visual thinking and analyzing potential audiences helped them find a common understanding. The technology student continued working on the data analysis, finding the former resolutions, trying different algorithms and visual effects. He only had a few categories and parameters of these SNS data, like friend number, visit number, share number and topics. These seemed too simple to create the beautiful effect in the eyes of the design student, but it was hard work for the technology student. Although at the beginning of the project, students don't have intersecting ideas; through the process, they try to bring their ideas closer from the opposite sides. The most important thing for an interdisciplinary team is to find the solution path between opposite or different sides. The potential ideas or solutions just like dots in a map; there is no straight line, but the zigzag or iterative paths go through these dots to reach the final goal. This path finally shows the trail of holistic design thinking. See Figure 4.

Figure 4. Model for holistic Design Thinking

After working for a few weeks, they created several rough prototypes, which provide a common base for further development. In the later stages, the students began to reconsider the meaning and value of a visual model, and tried to explain some social issues based on this model. Although the final effect is quite different from their initial expectation, but they built a three-dimensional model, added social relationships to the model and found a valuable application possibility in the Business-to-Business field. A paper based on this research was accepted by EVA 2011 London conference, which is the first paper on this conference from China in the past 5 years. See Figure 5.

Figure 5. Case B: The Visualization of Mass Information in Social Network with a Holistic View

DISCUSSIONS ON INTERDISCIPLINARY LEARNING MODELS

The final target of this interdisciplinary program is to cultivate interdisciplinary talents. To better understand the learning features of interdisciplinary work, we tracked the development of their team communication skills, ways of design thinking in the

Project Practice series courses, knowledge transfer and structuring process and innovative mode in the practice. Project Practice series courses include three independent courses, which respectively focus on methodology study, practical application, and integrating innovation. Team communication skill is quite important for knowledge transfer and the development of new design methods. The process of research and design is to rethink constantly in the practice and finally to practice reflection.

TEAM WORK AND SHARED LANGUAGE

A typical interdisciplinary graduate team is usually composed of graduates with design and technological backgrounds. Design graduates can show their skill with research and planning, while technological graduates show their capability in practice.

Considering the different backgrounds of the students, in the practice project courses, we adopt a top-down research method. For example, we prefer to think about project significance and the users' experience rather than abstract concepts. This is more helpful for achieving a common understanding between team members.

The biggest challenge for a team is to solve the problem of communication. In the class, we tend to consider communication as a process. We promote students to spend more time on the search for multiple directions rather than coming into a common answer before the next step. Students need the practical results of multiple attempts to solve the conflicts. They do design more effectively based on the application situation and rapid prototype. This is useful in solving the communication and linguistic problems and finally forming a generally accepted language in team.

In an interdisciplinary team, the graduate with a design background often acts as a facilitator and the graduate with a technological background often plays the role of revealing the innovation of unknown fields. They persuade and discuss with each other, supplement and extend on other disciplines and also further extend the knowledge of their own discipline during the discussion.

For the technology-driven projects of information visualization project based on data mining, designers need to know the advantages and disadvantages of technology and to try every possibility together with

students of technological background during the whole design process. In such a case, to break through an existing technological concept and constantly rethink with respect to social significance, user and cultural values can make it easier to determine the direction of the project.

HOLISTIC DESIGN THINKING

Through communication, after a common vision and target are agreed on, the team also needs a common thinking methodology. Design thinking is helpful in forming an understandable common methodology. "Design thinking is a means of clarifying the way things are today, and giving shape to your vision of how things can be tomorrow." (Form CMU Tepper school summer programs, 2011)

Design thinking has become a new interdisciplinary tool and is developing into a new concept and way of thinking to solve problems for many disciplines. Design thinking provides the common innovative methods for the design, engineering and business background students. Tim Brown advocates using the three stages of "design thinking": inspiration, ideation and implementation. But in an interdisciplinary team, design thinking can't be divided with the clear stages; it is holistic thinking based on different perspectives and an iterative process. The final goal is also not clear before you reach it.

It's found in the teaching that to have participants with different backgrounds is helpful in developing a common thinking when discussing facts and basis of creation. The description by professional terminology needs the way of "in other words" to "translate" into the general words students with other backgrounds can understand. Or it adopts the way of vision description to make students of different orientations know the final direction and to be helpful to achieve a common ground. For instance, methods of storytelling, body storming and speed dating are for a better understanding in the initial stage of design.

In project practice, many problems are not with a single solution. Diversified vision and solution are helpful to integrate all the existing resources to achieve the best outcome. The process of design thinking is not simple induction or deduction inference, but a process of abduction. When students

are doing brainstorming or future target setting, it shall adopt abduction inference to think the relations among the outcome, the situation and the rules (Peirce, 1992). Especially in the Project Practice 1 and 2, when students have already learnt design rules and known the outcome and need to find application context for the design, abduction inference is quite important. But in practical operation, to use induction or deduction inference is helpful for the prototype and design realization.

INTEGRATED KNOWLEDGE NETWORKING

According to the research on design process done by Donald Schön (Donald Schön, 1987), design thinking and practice are based on reflection. Students will build up his knowledge system through the ideas of knowing-in-action and reflection-in-action. In knowledge structure building, transferring across different disciplines and promoting new interdisciplinary fields are very important. For instance, for a graduate with journalism or literature background, it is not for him/her to learn and master programming language and interactive technology, but to understand the design thought and the whole innovative procedure, to develop the capability of communicating with a student with different background from himself. These capabilities are the base for his work in an interdisciplinary team in the future. At the same time, he/she shall also take advantage of their own capabilities and think about the influence of social media and interactive technology from the perspective of society and culture. This also matches the orientation of interdisciplinary training - design and social innovation.

If the interdisciplinary talents can be represented by figure “T”, the vertical line would represent their specialty, which could be design, computer science, engineering, media, literature and management. The horizontal line represents the interdisciplinary research capability they developed during the graduate study. The crossing between the vertical and horizontal lines represents the interdisciplinary method fields, namely the training of design thinking and practice of cooperative projects. Their capability represented by the vertical line shows the core contribution of a graduate in a team. Horizontal

line indicates the capability of cooperating and creating in interdisciplinary circumstances. However, in the interdisciplinary program, we found that these T-shaped people didn’t deepen their skill in vertical specialty, but develop more experiences on application and socialization. These experiences help different background students to work together and develop thinking more than one side. Every student has their position in team, and interdisciplinary training will help them to connect with other members. One student may not work for the comprehensive project but they will create unexpected possibilities when we join them together in a team. They will promote the design system and process as whole fields. See Figure 6.

Figure 6. Training T-shaped Talents in interdisciplinary knowledge fields

Currently for such talent, the opportunities in employment may not correspond exactly to a certain position, but facing the potential development they will own greater opportunities in significant cross-disciplinary projects in China.

In the training of interdisciplinary graduates, we should also help students with different backgrounds find the most suitable way for his development. For personalized education, in our Project Practice courses we choose projects and topics direction according based on the actual situation of the

students. For instance, students with design background will be trained more towards planning and management, while those with technological background towards development and application capabilities. By this way we can help them find their positions quickly and possess the potential of sustainable development in industry in the future.

INNOVATION IN PRACTICE

In the interdisciplinary education, we highlight the importance of iteration and focus on the innovation in application and practice. David Kolb (Kolb, 1984) believes that learning is not the acquiring and transmitting of content, but a process from experience transfer to knowledge creation. Learning is in iterative mode. The practice focuses on iterations of creation of that need to integrate users' actual experience, to observe and rethink design, to conclude the concepts and ideas during creation step by step, and to test the meaning of the new concept in new environment.

The meaning of practice is to use innovation to change the copying habit in Chinese design and to solve the problem of "copy to China". We need to review it in respect of the society, economy and technical integration. Innovation will come from Chinese culture and society. Therefore, the training of interdisciplinary teams shall highlight the integration of social responsibility and integrity with technology, as well as the integration of new technology with commercial mode and innovation in application.

Students of different qualities work together and learn from each other. This is good for innovation. To make use of one's advantage in one field into another field is a kind of innovation. For instance, graduates with the backgrounds of computer science and visual communication working together can better integrate interaction technology and social media, so as to improve communication and social function of intelligent interface.

In project practice, ability of implementing is also quite important. It requires good management and planning of the project through designing major pattern of whole process, leading in stages, and rapid prototyping.

For instance, the project adopts parallel method. After the procedure and work division is determined,

different people will lead the project at different stages. However, it needs to be ensured that all team members participate the whole process. They bring their own strengths into play and know the background of others in order to achieve more influences in the team. The design highlights the whole picture, but the technology is detail-oriented. At the initial stage of the project, it needs to strengthen the coordination, instruction and project management to prevent the initial stage from lasting for too long and influencing the schedule.

The interdisciplinary graduates possess different disciplinary backgrounds, thinking methods and working styles. Through project practice and joint research, they can form a coordinating, cooperative and harmonious team that can make their own advantages into full play. For every individual student, he/she shall also find out his own direction of development after graduation. These are the keys for interdisciplinary education.

CONCLUSION

In general, the training model of interdisciplinary master program is for graduates with different backgrounds. Under the joint instruction of Supervisor group, through taking design thinking and research methods courses, studio class on social and business innovation, students are able to come up with innovative solutions to different frontier issues and complete their design outcomes that are of high social influence.

In the training of interdisciplinary graduates, teamwork, design thinking, knowledge structure and integrated innovation are the highlights. In teamwork, students of different backgrounds learn from each other, share their knowledge and experiences, so as to develop common shared language and way of thinking, which is the core of the interdisciplinary training.

As for project-driven subjects, interdisciplinary graduates will focus on exploring and solving wicked social and complicated cultural issues. Graduates develop research through design, try to understand the subject from different point of views, build up innovation knowledge structure and develop the capability of managing and controlling the whole picture of the project process.

As for the concept of interdisciplinary teaching, it is not simply teaching technology background students to learn arts, or students of art background to learn technology, but the capability of surpassing a single discipline, promoting knowledge integration, forming common methodology and facilitating interdisciplinary “chemical reaction”. Based on the prospective need of future development of the industries and enterprises, it establishes a new design platform, explores a common research and design pattern crossing over the design, technology and media platforms and promotes the social and business innovation based on its project driven courses. Therefore, it can reserve the interdisciplinary talents for realizing the policy of innovation nation in different professionals, and cultivate more diversified designers with social responsibility for the sustainable environment and inclusive development in China.

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